

Emergency Surgical Management of Aorto-Duodenal Fistula Causing Massive Gastrointestinal Hemorrhage

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Introduction

Aortoenteric fistulas are life-threatening cause of gastrointestinal bleeding, resulting from erosion of the aortic wall into the adjacent intestinal tract and leading to massive hemorrhage.

Case Presentation

A 65-year-old male presented to the hospital in hemorrhagic shock of unknown origin. Laboratory investigations revealed severe anemia, with hemoglobin levels below 3 g/dL, and a prolonged activated partial thromboplastin time, indicating a high risk of spontaneous bleeding. After initial hemodynamic stabilization and blood transfusion, computed tomography angiography identified an aortoduodenal fistula. Therapeutic options included extra-anatomical bypass with aortic ligation, which is associated with high mortality, or in situ aortic reconstruction with a prosthetic vascular graft. In this case, the second option was selected and performed as an emergency procedure, in association with duodenorrhaphy. Intraoperatively, the third part of the duodenum, the inframesocolic aorta, and the inferior vena cava were dissected. The fistulous tract was identified and clamped, and the duodenum was prepared for duodenorrhaphy. Dissection of the aorta was then continued proximally. The aorta was clamped both proximally and distally. The fistulous tract was located between the aorta and the inferior vena cava, which was carefully dissected and retracted laterally to allow adequate exposure of the aorta.

Conclusion

This case highlights the importance of rapid recognition and prompt surgical management in aorto-duodenal fistula, demonstrating the successful outcomes are possible even in critically ill patients with massive gastrointestinal hemorrhage.

Keywords

Aortoenteric fistula, haemorrhagic shock, vascular grafting, duodenorrhaphy